

WATER-ASSISTED COMPOUNDING OF COFFEE GROUNDS FOR THERMOFORMING CUPS

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ABSTRACT

Packaging comprises around 40% of global plastics consumption. Because the world's rivers and lakes and especially its oceans are heavily polluted with plastics, society is pressing the industry to make more sustainable products. Coffee is consumed in large amounts, and the plastic coffee cup is an eye-catching example in many discussions of plastic waste. Therefore, it would be a nice idea to kill two birds with one stone by using recycled coffee grounds in producing the cups; furthermore, it would be a step towards the circular economy. This paper presents a new technology for using spent coffee grounds in a polystyrene compound for thermoforming vending coffee cups. The technology uses water-assisted compounding to produce the composite in a co-rotating twin-screw extruder, the standard machine for plastics compounding. Injection-moulded tensile-testing bars were produced for evaluating the material properties. The fracture surface was analysed by optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy in order to determine the size of the particles and the quality of their bonding to the matrix. The new compound fulfilled the specifications. The proof of concept was demonstrated in a production test on a high performance line. This produced three-layered coffee cups, the middle layer filled with 10% spent coffee grounds instead of a mineral filler.

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2017 the world consumed 348 million tonnes of plastics, of which Europe consumed 51 million tonnes, or about 15%; and 40% of Europe's total comprised of packaging [1]. Packaging comprises a large fraction of global plastics consumption. The producers of plastic packaging at present face a double challenge: first the economic pressure to produce at lower cost, and second society's global demand to reduce the carbon footprint and solve the problem of polluting the oceans with waste plastic. Some researchers even assert that synthetic polymers in the ocean should be regarded as hazardous waste [2].

Because packaging represents the largest converter demand [1], packaging items - especially single-use items - are the subject of political discussions and bans all over the world. An example is the ban on single-use plastic items approved by the European Parliament [3]. Despite this, disposable coffee cups will remain a problem for many years. Coffee, grown in about eighty countries, is one of the world's most popular beverages and the second-largest traded commodity from developing countries after petroleum [4]. Coffee silverskin and spent coffee grounds (SCG) are significant waste products of the coffee industry [5, 6]. Our focus here is on spent coffee grounds, which are the main by-product. A huge amount of coffee grounds results from brewing coffee, and there is at present no effective way

of re-using them. Therefore it would be a nice idea to kill two birds with one stone by using recycled coffee grounds in producing the cups; furthermore, it would be a step towards the circular economy.

Because of the large amount of this material, which is mainly either burned off or buried in landfill, many studies have been made in recent decades to find a way of re-using it. Most of these have focussed on biomass or biofuel [5–7]. Some of these studies aim at using the coffee grounds as a filler for injection-moulded articles, of which the wall thickness is typically over 1 mm [8].

It is estimated that over 500 billion plastic cups are produced every year and an additional 16 billion disposable coffee cups, mostly with a thin plastic layer inside [9]. The cups are mostly made out of paper or plastics, those used in automatic coffee dispensers being universally made of plastics. Today the market is dominated by cups made of polystyrene (PS), whose strength, high thermal resistance and glossy appearance make it ideal for hot drinks.

2 MATERIALS, METHODS AND PRODUCT

2.1 Coffee Grounds

Coffee cherries are the raw fruit of the coffee plant, and are composed of two coffee beans covered by a thin parchment-like hull and further surrounded by pulp. These cherries are usually harvested from coffee trees at least five years old, when they turn red [10]. “Coffee” is the designation of the drink prepared by extraction, in boiling water, of the soluble material from roasted and ground beans. There are many different coffee brewing methods in the world. Coffee beverage can be prepared, for example, by the filtration–percolation method, in which ground coffee is placed on a specific support grid (filter paper, muslin, perforated plastic filter, sintered glass, etc.) and the coffee extracted by dripping or spraying with hot water, i.e., by slow gravity percolation. This is the method used in most coffee machines [6].

The spent coffee grounds used in this study came from an industrial coffee-brewing process, with a particle size up to 1 mm and a moisture content between 50% and 60%. Figure 1 shows typical particle size distributions.

Figure 1: Particle size distribution of spent coffee grounds for different coffee types [11]

2.2 Thermoforming vending coffee cups

Vending coffee cups are designed for vending automats and table-top vending machines. They come in many different styles, but all of them have to do the job with 100% reliability. The reason is that if a problem occurs, the vending machine is stopped and a service person has to come to repair it. For example it is very important that they can be stacked in a small space and that they unstack easily and reliably.

Cups are produced today in multi-mould thermoforming machines. A single production line can produce up to 600 kg/h, which represents over 100,000 cups per hour. Table 1 shows a well known standard vending cup and its specifications.

	Vending Cup	
	Article Number	139
	Content	180 cm ³
	Diameter	70.3 mm
	Height	91 mm
	Articles per stack	100 cups

Table 1: Specification of Vending cup Art. No. 109 [12]

The feedstock is typically a three-layer sheet with the outer layers of PS and the middle layer of high-impact PS filled with calcium carbonate.

Thermoforming a coffee cup with a filled material is a challenge. The draw-down ratio is quite high, with the final wall thickness less than one-fifth of the original sheet thickness. During forming the material needs excellent ductility in relation to its strength in order to achieve uniform thickness. For this reason it is necessary to reduce the grain size of SCG in order to be able to use them as a filler. At present the middle layer is filled with 20% by weight mineral filler. Owing to the difference in density between the mineral filler and spent coffee grounds a composite was desired having 10% by weight of filler.

2.3 Compounding by using water-assisted extrusion

Water-assisted extrusion has been quoted for several years now as a means of achieving a good dispersion in mineral- or bio-nanocomposites in order to avoid agglomeration and solve the safety problems associated with nanoscale powders [13–24].

If water-based grinding of particles is the only way of reducing particle size, water-assisted compounding is an excellent solution. It combines all the advantages of good dispersion and of safe operation with low capital and operating costs.

Although most of the current research on water-assisted compounding is in the area of nanoscale materials, it could also be of interest to investigate microscale particle materials should problems arise in processing with dry fibres or during the drying process.

Generally, four different methods are available for adding water to the compounding process section:

- A) Water is injected into the molten polymer in the process section. This degassing process in the polymer industry is known as a stripping process, to optimize the degassing of monomers [25]
- B) Water is additionally injected to the process section. Polymer and nanoclay is fed in the first barrel. [15, 22].
- C) Water suspension is fed to the first barrel of the compounder. This process is reported in several studies in the field of nanoclay processing, as well in the processing of nanocellulose [18, 26, 13, 14, 19, 24, 27]. The optimal compounding technique is the same whether the melt is pelletized or compression-moulded afterwards.
- D) Water suspension is injected into the molten plastic. This technique is quoted in several studies in the field of nanoclay processing [17, 15, 21], as well in the processing of nanocellulose [26, 23, 27]. This is the process chosen for use with SCG.

The four methods are illustrated in Figure 2. A heterogeneous mixture of liquid and fine dispersed particles is named a suspension. The particles may be visible to the naked eye, must usually be larger than one micrometre, and will eventually settle, although the mixture is only classified as a suspension when and while the particles have not settled out [28]. In material science, a suspension in water is termed a slurry.

Figure 2: Schematic views of the four possible ways of adding water to the compounding process.

- A) Stripping process
- B) Water is added additionally to the compounding of polymer and particles
- C) Water suspension is fed together with the polymer to the first barrel
- D) Water suspension is pumped into the molten polymer

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Reducing the particle size of spent coffee grounds

First mechanical dry grinding with rotary knives was tried, but because of the oil and fatty acids [7] in the SCG, it proved impossible to achieve a uniform small grain-size distribution. The sieves were blocked immediately and the grinding process stopped.

Therefore an alternative had to be found. One possibility is to use a water-based grinding system (refiner) for reducing particle size, as in the field of nano- and microfibrillated cellulose [6]. At the Weidmann Fiber Technology Division of Weidmann Electrical Technology AG the SCG were first dispersed in water and diluted to a solids content of 15 % by weight. They were then ground for seven hours, using a high shear force treatment with a net energy input of 320 kWh/t. In contrast to cellulose pulp, which is used as a raw material for the production of nano- and micro-fibrillated cellulose, SCG do not contain a lot of fibrillar structures. Therefore, the SCG were reduced in this manner to particles mostly 50-300 microns in diameter but not fibrillated, as shown in Figure 3. A viscous water-based paste was obtained, as seen in Figure 4. This suspension had a viscosity of 1000 mPa.s as measured on a Brookfield DV2T.

SCG dispersed in water
before grinding

SCG dispersed in water
after 7 hours of grinding

Figure 3: Comparison of SCG dispersed in water, before and after 7 hours of grinding

Figure 4: Spent coffee grounds reduced in size by a water-based grinding operation

Figure 5 shows the fibre-length distribution of the ground SCG particles, most of the particles having a fibre-length in the range 0.05 to 0.3 mm.

Figure 5: Achieved fibre-length distribution of the ground SCG

3.2 Compounding

The compounding was carried out on a Coperion ZSK 26 Mc co-rotating twin-screw extruder with a process length of 44 L/D (length/diameter). The compound was made with a high-impact polystyrene (HIPS Styron A-Technology 1200) and a coffee grounds slurry having 15% solids by weight and 85% water.

Figure 6: The ZSK 26MC Compounder equipped with an EUP 50 underwater pelletizer that was used for the trials

Figure 7 shows the details of the compounding. The molten polymer was fed into the first barrel and mixed by kneading blocks in barrels 2 and 3. The suspension of water and ground SCG was pumped in at barrel 4, via an injection nozzle of our own design and construction. In barrels 5 to 9 the suspension was mixed with the polystyrene melt, and the water was first removed by atmospheric venting and then evaporated at the vacuum port at barrel 10. Barrel 11 served to build up the required pressure for the ECON EUP 50 underwater pelletizer (see Figure 6). The test was run at 300 rpm with a machine load of 50%, and the barrel temperature varied between 180°C and 200°C.

Figure 7: Screw configuration of ZSK 26MC

The HIPS polymer was fed at 13.5 kg/h and the suspension at 10 kg/h. The suspension comprising of 15% of SCG by weight, the feed rate of dry spent coffee grounds was thus 1.5 kg/h giving a total throughput rate of 15 kg/h. The resulting composite contained 10% by weight of SCG.

3.3 Characterisation of the compound

First the PS/SCG10% compound was injection moulded on a Battenfeld SP60/210 Unilog B6. Standard tensile bars were produced according to EN ISO 527 [29] and conditioned according to EN ISO 179 [30]. Tensile strength, elongation at rupture and E-modulus were determined on a SHIMADZU Autograph AG-X plus equipped with a 50 kN load cell, and impact strength on an ANSE impact testing machine equipped with a 7.5 J hammer. Since there was not enough material to do all the tests with the PS/SCG10% compound, for some tests a diluted PS/SCG6% sample was created (see Table 2). As expected, the filler increased the E-Modulus. The effect on the tensile strength was minor, but the elongation at break decreased significantly. It is noteworthy that the values with 6% of SCG seem to be better than those with 10%, and this effect is being investigated further.

Material	E-Modules [MPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]	Notched Charpy [kJ/m ²]
HIPS	1743	26.1	55	16.5
PS/SCG6%	2068	25.4	31	11.3
PS/SCG10%	2046	24.8	24	12.6

Table 2: Mechanical Properties of PS/SCG compared with those of neat HIPS

The fracture surface was analysed by optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy in order to determine the size of the particles and the quality of their bonding to the matrix. For the optical microscopy a Keyence VHX-600 was used, while a Hitachi TM1000 table SEM was employed to analyse the surface morphology of the PS/SCG10% samples, as shown in Figure 8. The results for the PS/SCG6% were similar.

Figure 8: Images of the fracture surface of the same PS/SCG10% sample with an agglomerate visible in the middle. The first two are from optical microscopy at low and high magnification, and the third from the SEM.

The compound fulfilled the specification: the values achieved are comparable with those of the mineral-filled compounds.

3.4 Sheet extrusion

The first three-layer sheet extrusion in the test series was performed on a Collin Chill Roll CR 136/450 S with a 400 mm wide die and a three-layer feed block. Extrusion presented no major problems and the planned three-layer composite was produced comparable with the standard sheet. Impressions of the equipment used in the pilot run are shown in Figure 9.

Two sample films were produced, with a width of 292 mm and thickness of 0.8 mm to a tolerance of ± 0.05 mm.

Table 3 shows the details of the composition of the sample films. The test run went well, and more than ten metres of each sample were produced.

Film Number	Layer A		Layer B		Layer C	
	[%]	Material	[%]	Material	[%]	Material
2-1	20	HIPS	60	PS/SCG10%	20	HIPS
2-2	60	PS/SCG10%	20	HIPS	20	HIPS

Table 3: Composition of the sample films 2-1 and 2-2

Figure 9: Impressions of the pilot extrusion of three-layered sheets with the PS/SCG10% layer

3.5 Thermoforming

In a first step on a pilot thermoforming line with a single cavity mould, an 80 mm high cup was produced with a diameter of 70 mm and a wall thickness of 0.3 mm. The pilot run went very well. Cups were produced using sheet made with the water-assisted grinding and compounding recipe, and others with sheet made with sieved SCG. Figure 10 shows one of each. To show the difference a hot water test was performed. The cups made using sieved SCG were even leaking: they have little holes. It would be impossible to use them.

Figure 10: A) Cup produced in the pilot trial with PS/SCG10% with water assisted grinding and compounding. B) Cup thermoformed from sheet made with sieved SCG without water assistance.

4 PRODUCTION TEST

To demonstrate the potential and the quality of the composite, a production run was made with a 54-cavity mould on an inline sheet extrusion and thermoforming machine running at 34 strokes per minute. This machine has a production capacity of more than 100,000 cups per hour. First a three-layer sheet analogous to sample film 2-2 was produced and then directly thermoformed on the 54-cavity line, as shown in Figure 11 left. The cups produced (Figure 11 right) fulfilled the specifications. Beside the mechanical tests, food safety tests were carried out.

Figure 11: Production test on the in-line extrusion and 54-cavity thermoforming line (left), resulting cup (right)

6 CONCLUSIONS

By using water-assisted extrusion it was possible to obtain a PS/CSG composite with micro-scale particles, with which cups could be satisfactorily thermoformed. However, the process needs to be optimized for scaling-up to higher throughput rates.

The market response to the vending cups filled with 10% spent coffee grounds is very positive. Development and testing continues.

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